

The Importance of Interdisciplinary Knowledge in Architecture, Construction and Transportation in Human Resource Training for the Southeastern Region of Vietnam

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Abstract

The integration of interdisciplinary courses in architecture, construction engineering and transportation engineering within training programs is extremely important and necessary in the current context of urban and infrastructure development. The main objective is to educate a generation of architects and engineers with systems thinking and the ability to solve complex, multidimensional problems in an era of rapid development of AI-based design technologies and new construction technologies.

This paper studies and proposes solutions and new approaches to strengthen interdisciplinarity in the architecture, construction and transportation training programs of the Faculty of Architecture and Construction, Thu Dau Mot University. The aim is to equip students with interdisciplinary knowledge and skills so that they can solve the problems arising in real-world projects.

Keywords: *Training, transportation, architecture, interdisciplinary, construction.*

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Introduction

The relationship between the training disciplines of architecture, construction and transportation is at the core of the complexity of urban planning and development. These factors do not exist independently but constantly interact, constrain and complement each other, forming a complex urban ecosystem:

- Unique architectural designs, which tend to require large spans to create wide spaces and have complex façades, pose major challenges in terms of structural systems, materials and

construction methods, thereby increasing project costs and risk.

- The planning of a major road, overpass, or metro/urban railway station constrains the form, height and location of buildings as well as their foundation and structural solutions.
- The construction of a high-rise building requires management of material transportation to the site, directly and significantly affecting the existing urban traffic network in the locality.

The use of interdisciplinary knowledge helps students gain a clearer understanding of their

own discipline while consolidating their knowledge of closely related specialties linked to their future job positions. At the same time, interdisciplinary knowledge makes learning more convenient, enabling students to be more proactive in arranging timetables for interdisciplinary modules and avoiding having to wait for courses to be offered on the general schedule of each separate program. Taking interdisciplinary modules together with students from other disciplines also makes it easier for them to remember and master the content.

Teaching interdisciplinary modules enables lecturers to apply diverse and more effective teaching methods, because the student cohort is no longer limited to a single discipline but includes different majors that are strongly correlated with one another in terms of future job positions.

Training in isolation and without sufficient linkage between architecture, construction and transportation leads to serious limitations in the skills of graduates, especially their ability to coordinate and solve complex problems in real urban development contexts:

- Architecture students lack in-depth knowledge of structural feasibility, project cost and construction risk, which may result in building designs that are aesthetically pleasing but unrealistic or prohibitively expensive to build.
- Construction students may not fully understand architectural aesthetics or the overall context of urban and transport planning, causing engineers to focus solely on technical aspects while overlooking functional and social factors.
- Transportation students may lack knowledge of land-use planning and building density, leading to traffic solutions that are not synchronized with spatial development in the surrounding area.

Currently, the Faculty of Architecture and Construction, Thu Dau Mot University, offers four training programs:

- Architecture program (Architect)

- Construction Engineering program (Construction Engineer)
- Wood Processing Technology program (Furniture Design Engineer)
- Traffic Construction Engineering program (Transportation/Bridge and Road Engineer)

Materials and Methods

This study uses analytical and synthetic methods, based on secondary documents on the importance of interdisciplinary knowledge for improving the quality of training for students in architecture, construction and transportation.

Analytical methods are used to examine key issues in order to enhance the effectiveness of interdisciplinary modules in the architecture, construction and transportation programs of the Faculty of Architecture and Construction, Thu Dau Mot University. Survey data were collected from students and alumni of the faculty.

These data are used to identify the main issues that need to be addressed in order to improve training quality in the block of interdisciplinary knowledge for architecture, construction and transportation students, ensuring that graduates can quickly take on their work in the context of rapid digitalization, integration and cross-fertilization among these sectors globally.

Overview

As the country enters a new era of development, science, technology and innovation play a key role in promoting comprehensive national growth. The Southeast region is considered one of the most dynamic economic zones in Vietnam. In addition to strong development in education, the economy and services, technical infrastructure — especially architecture, construction and transportation — holds a central position in driving socio-economic development. This process not only brings about a clear transformation for the architecture, construction and transportation sectors in connection with regional economic growth, but also requires comprehensive and breakthrough application of scientific and technological advances and innovation. At the same time, it

must be harmoniously combined with cultural factors to ensure sustainable development and a balance between technology and social identity. Faced with these new requirements, improving the quality of human resource training becomes a central and necessary task to build a workforce of engineers and architects with solid professional competence, practical skills and the ability to integrate internationally.

With its development orientation and strategic vision, Thu Dau Mot University aims to become a center of culture, education, science and technology, providing high-quality human resources and scientific and technological products to serve socio-economic development and international integration in Ho Chi Minh City, the Southeast region and the whole country. To meet this strategy, the leadership of the Faculty of Architecture and Construction has set goals for developing high-quality human resources in architecture, construction engineering, traffic construction engineering and wood processing technology, in order to satisfy the rising demand of the labor market and society in the context of the ongoing Fourth Industrial Revolution.

The main challenges in integrating knowledge in architecture, construction and transportation include:

- Conflicting objectives: the architect's goal is the aesthetics and spatial functionality of

the building and urban area; the construction engineer's goal is technical feasibility and cost optimization; the transportation engineer's goal is traffic capacity for bridges and roads as well as the efficiency of the urban traffic network. Reconciling all of these goals is extremely difficult.

- Lack of synchronization between practice software: modeling tools in architecture (for example Revit, SketchUp) typically focus on form and volume, while tools used in transportation (such as Vissim, Civil 3D) focus on terrain, alignments and traffic flow. Integrating data between these platforms remains challenging, especially for large-scale projects.

Labor market demand for experts with interdisciplinary knowledge — particularly at the intersection of architecture, construction and transportation — is rising rapidly and has become a mandatory requirement in many large corporations. This reflects a shift from implementing isolated projects to developing integrated systems and urban environments.

"Traditional disciplinary boundaries are being broken. Graduates must have multidisciplinary knowledge so they can work in many different positions, or in a single position that requires multiple skills and knowledge, and they must be lifelong self-learners."

Table 1. Interdisciplinary Courses

Interdisciplinary course			
A	Industry basis	B	specialized
1	Descriptive Geometry, straight projection (2+0)	1	Legal in planning and construction (2+0)
2	Research Method (3+0)	2	Construction Methods (3+0)
3	Civil engineering materials (2+0)	3	Construction management (2+0)
4	Construction Material Laboratory Tests (0+1)	4	Construction Estimates (2+0)
5	Structure Overview (2+0)	5	Project planning and appraisal (2+0)
6	Principles of architectural design and industrial structure (3+0)	6	Technical system and equipments of building (3+0)

Research Results

Level of Understanding of Construction and Transportation Interdisciplinary Knowledge among Architecture Students and Alumni

The results in Table 2 show that the responses from architecture students regarding construction and transportation interdisciplinary knowledge reached an above-average level on the measured factors. The most positive factor is

understanding of principles of traffic design and public space around buildings. This is consistent with the fact that, in spatial and landscape design

projects, architecture students are equipped with knowledge related to the design of walkways and circulation within buildings.

Table 2. Survey Results on the Level of Understanding of Construction and Transportation Interdisciplinary Knowledge among Architecture Students and Alumni

Content	Average
Factors affecting the cost and difficulty of structural construction	3.08
Ability to read and understand structural drawings (beams, columns, foundations) and related technical symbols	3.16
Understanding of material standards (strength grades of concrete and steel) and their impact on the durability of structures	3.21
Understanding of traffic safety corridors, regulations on road connections and their impact on building locations	3.32
Understanding of principles of traffic design and public space around buildings	3.34

However, there are still limitations in criteria such as the ability to read and understand structural drawings and factors affecting the cost and difficulty of structural construction. This indicates a need to improve teaching methods and assessment forms in modules related to these criteria so that architecture students can be

more effectively equipped with construction-related interdisciplinary knowledge.

Level of Understanding of Architectural Interdisciplinary Knowledge among Construction and Transportation Students

Table 3. Survey Results on the Level of Understanding of Architectural Interdisciplinary Knowledge among Construction and Transportation Students and Alumni

Content	Average
Ability to read and understand architectural design intent (aesthetics, function, spatial solutions)	3.35
Understanding of architectural design standards for buildings	3.47
Understanding of building envelope solutions	3.29
Understanding of finishing materials in buildings	3.15
Understanding of principles of green and sustainable building design	3.41

The results in Table 3 show that the responses from construction and transportation students and alumni regarding architectural interdisciplinary knowledge also reached an above-average level on the measured factors. Understanding of architectural standards is the strongest factor, which is reasonable because the ability to read codes and standards is one of the expected learning outcomes for students in engineering disciplines. However, the weakest factor is understanding of finishing materials in

buildings, indicating that students have not been adequately equipped, or have not proactively equipped themselves, with knowledge about finishing materials. Finishing materials constitute one component of the loads acting on a structure and are also an important factor in the architectural aesthetics of a building.

Ability to Apply Interdisciplinary Knowledge to Solve Practical Problems

Table 4. Survey Results on the Ability to Apply interdisciplinary Knowledge to Solve Practical Problems

Content	Average
When faced with a practical problem, can you analyze it from the perspectives of different disciplines?	3.51
Self-assessed proficiency in using interdisciplinary knowledge to perform work tasks	3.28
Level of confidence when presenting a complex problem involving multiple disciplines ?	3.76

Ability to collaborate with people with different specializations	3.85
Ability to use multidisciplinary software tools	3.31

The results in Table 4 show that group-work skills and the ability to collaborate with people of different specializations are rated highly, indicating that learners have been equipped with good teamwork skills. However, there are limitations in students' self-assessed proficiency in using interdisciplinary knowledge to perform work tasks. This suggests that the block of

interdisciplinary subjects currently implemented in the programs has not been fully effective, and there remain shortcomings in the teaching and learning process.

Training Programs that should be Strengthened with Interdisciplinary Integration

Table 5. Survey Results on Strengthening Interdisciplinary Integration in the Training Programs

Content	Average
New technology (AI, Big Data, IoT)	4.21
Interdisciplinary project management knowledge block	4.17
Foreign languages	3.19
Legal knowledge block	3.52

The results in Table 5 indicate that equipping students with knowledge of new technologies (AI, Big Data, IoT) is the most highly valued factor. This reflects the urgent need to keep pace with current development trends in all professions. Knowledge of new technologies helps students avoid falling behind, enhances their value in the labor market, and contributes to delivering high-quality, sustainable and smart projects.

Proposed Solutions

Organizing Competitions for Students of All Majors

To increase the ability to apply interdisciplinary knowledge for students of the Faculty of Architecture and Construction, and to bring excitement after theoretical lessons on both interdisciplinary and specialized subjects, the

faculty annually cooperates with companies in interior and exterior design consultancy, construction companies in civil and industrial works, wood manufacturing companies, etc., in Ho Chi Minh City and the Southeast region to regularly organize academic competitions. These contests are open to all students in the faculty, the university and other universities in Ho Chi Minh City in relevant fields such as architecture, urban planning, construction, fine arts, graphic design and wood technology.

These competitions provide academic playgrounds where students can exchange and discuss, consolidate the knowledge they have learned and draw experience from their own shortcomings. At the same time, they create opportunities for students to interact with alumni and practitioners working in companies.

Table 6. Competitions for Students

Year	Competitions for students
2022 - 2023	- Public space for everyone – landscape of Bach Dang walking street toilet Binh Duong province - Structural creation season 1
2023 - 2024	- Fast construction - Architectural design data analysis - Structural creation season 2
2024-2025.	- Design of Thu Dau Mot University gate - Structural creation season 3

2025-2026	- Industrial wood - specialized solutions for kitchen interior design and construction ideas
	- Industrial wood - specialized solutions for apartment interior design and construction ideas

Organizing Industry Talks from Enterprises for Students

Industry talks help students understand their profession more deeply, including the advantages and challenges of working as an architect. Business leaders share issues relating theory to practice so that students can grasp the current requirements of their chosen profession. These experiences help students realize what knowledge they need to study and cultivate.

At such seminars, scholars and business representatives share highly practical presentations. Speakers discuss their experience in implementing turnkey projects through professional processes, from market research

and building marketing strategies aligned with brand positioning to business planning and phased project implementation. The process includes developing design concepts based on real requirements, completing technical drawings, organizing construction, signing contracts and controlling site progress and quality. Speakers also emphasize that training programs should equip students not only with design skills but also with knowledge of management, marketing and customer care. This helps shape a generation of architects, construction engineers and transportation engineers with holistic thinking who can flexibly adapt to diverse and competitive working environments in the integration era.

Table 7. Student Talks

Year	Discussion content
2022 – 2023	- The evolution of building facades - Sharing experiences in designing high-rise architectural projects in Vietnam - Insee prize 2023, solutions for green buildings and project life cycle
2023 – 2024	- Application of AI technology in architectural design - Insee prize 2024, green buildings and practical applications - Aluminum and glass, modern architectural language - Design for Greater Efficiencies (DFGE), cooperation between IFC and Thu Dau Mot University
2024 – 2025	- Improving the quality of training in architecture, construction and transportation: practice and integration - Starting a business in the field of architecture and construction: Challenges and opportunities - Life cycle of construction materials and green buildings - Material and color trends in interior and exterior design
2025 – 2026	- Human resource needs and training orientations in the forest processing technology industry in the 4.0 technology era - Green building standards and their impact on material choice - key factors for sustainable development in the construction industry

Using Simulation Tool

With the rapid development of modeling and simulation software, students and lecturers can model buildings, bridges, stadiums, airport terminals, urban infrastructure systems, etc., in 2D and 3D on computers. However, for students to see their designs in the most intuitive and vivid way, virtual reality applications allow them to experience their projects in detail and in a more engaging manner.

Virtual reality enables students to walk through their designs in an interactive 3D environment. Compared with views that may not be clearly expressed in conventional 3D models, virtual reality can better reveal hidden corners and give students a more comprehensive view while highlighting key architectural details.

"The application of 3D modeling and virtual reality technologies is no longer an "option" but is becoming a mandatory factor for construction and architectural service companies that want to

keep pace with global trends. By approaching these technologies early, organizations can differentiate the customer experience, optimize implementation costs and enhance their competitiveness in the market."

Improving Lecturers' Expertise in Interdisciplinary Knowledge

To enhance lecturers' professional competence in line with the orientation of interdisciplinary training for architecture, construction, transportation and wood processing technology in the Faculty of Architecture and Construction during the Fourth Industrial Revolution and in accordance with labor market trends, several solutions can be implemented:

- Encourage lecturers to undertake professional internships and practical experience in enterprises. These activities help lecturers update practical knowledge, new technologies, production and business organization methods, services and real-world problem-solving skills. Through such programs, the university can promptly adjust curricula and teaching content to better reflect social needs and labor market requirements.
- Encourage lecturers to participate in interdisciplinary research projects so that they can gain practical experience in synthesizing knowledge from multiple sources.
- When designing lectures for interdisciplinary subjects, focus on core topics and real-world challenges common to all disciplines, particularly in the context of sustainable and smart urban development.

Updating the Training Curriculum Framework

"The curriculum determines the quality of human resources." The closer the curriculum aligns with social needs and employer requirements, the more effective it is in training human resources.

According to Decision No. 258/QĐ-TTg approving the roadmap for applying Building Information Modeling (BIM) in construction activities, from 2023 BIM is compulsory for Grade-I and special-grade works in new construction investment projects that use public

investment capital, state capital outside public investment, or public-private partnership capital, starting from the project preparation stage. In Phase 2, from 2025, BIM becomes compulsory for Grade-II works and above in similar types of projects.

Given the advantages that BIM offers in professional practice, the curriculum needs to be reviewed and supplemented with software practice modules that apply BIM technology so that students can quickly adapt to BIM when they enter the workforce. The following software is proposed for teaching:

- BIM for Architecture: Revit, Graphisoft Archicad
- BIM for Structures: Revit, Tekla, Robot Structural Analysis, STAAD.Pro
- BIM for Project Management: Navisworks Manage (+iConstruct + Synchro), Tekla BIMsight
- BIM for Transportation: Autodesk Civil 3D/InfraWorks, Bentley OpenRoads Designer.

Conclusion

Survey results have identified essential issues that need to be addressed so that interdisciplinary modules no longer pose learning obstacles for students. They also help students recognize subjective factors stemming from themselves as well as objective factors arising from lecturers' lesson content and teaching methods in interdisciplinary subjects, which currently do not fully meet students' needs.

The results also show that the faculty leadership and program coordinators always create favorable conditions for students to study more effectively through seminars and academic competitions. From the valuable experiences shared by previous generations, students realize that single-discipline knowledge is not sufficient and that they need to equip themselves with additional interdisciplinary knowledge relevant to their profession.

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